

ISic3570

I.Sicily inscription 3570

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance

hypogeum in contrada Rocciola-Scrofani (Cozzo Rotondo), eastern side of
Modica

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Modica, Museo Archeologico
Belgiorno, inventory 698

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337420

1. [— — — — — — — —]
2. [ἀπέθαν]εν τῆ [ς ἀπὸ]
3. [Κα]λανδῶν [— Ἀ]-
4. πριλίο[ν] {²⁷[Α] | πριλίο[υ]}²⁷ ἐπ[ὶ ἔ]-
5. τε ρη', μ[ῆ]νας ἔ]ζησεν [— —].
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645641
PHI 337420

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 54.0933

Rizzone, V.G., Sammito, A.M. 2005. Nuovi documenti epigrafici dal circondario di Modica. In Rizzo, F.P.(eds.), *Da abitato in abitato. In itinere fra le più antiche testimonianze cristiane degli Iblei*. Rome. pp. 45-62. At 53-54 fig.7

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